

Communicating Emotion in Design: The studio experience

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Abstract

This paper looks at the role emotion plays in design education and the studio experience in particular, from both a practical and theoretical perspective, at a time when design is migrating to the university environment. It draws from the author's experience of studio teaching and pedagogic research across a broad spectrum of design domains, and shows how emotion is embedded in the studio experience. It highlights the personal relationship design students have with their subject, and argues that emotional communication is critical to teacher-student interaction and learning outcomes. It compares the studio model with the lecture model and suggests that university-based design needs to raise emotional awareness in higher education discussions.

Conference theme: Emotion in design education

Keywords: emotional communication, learning styles, studio experience

Introduction

Emotion, as part of human nature, plays a role in everyday interaction. This may suggest that all cultures share the same set of basic emotions (Plana 1999). Each culture, however, also displays a unique set of emotions and emotional responses; the emotions shown in a particular culture reflects the norms, values, practices, and language of that culture. So while some human expressions of emotion have been identified as universal, such as joy, fear, anger, sadness, and surprise, many others are thought to be neither innate nor universal but complex cognitive constructs influenced and mediated by social and cultural factors (Ekman, 2003). Similarly, many behavioural and psychological theories, including emotional intelligence, combine the innate emotional variables, such as sensitivity, memory, processing and learning, with the environmental affects (Salovey and Mayer, 1990).

But while emotions are important phenomena in the study of psychology, there is no disciplinary consensus as to the definition of “emotion”. Emotion, then, is a complex phenomenon of both learned and innate expressive displays and physical responses that can be verbal as well as non-verbal, including body postures, attitudes and paralanguage, for example, hesitation and gesture. Emotional responses, moreover, may vary from total “openness” to “concealment”, for example, genuine versus social (“fake”) smiles, and can be very subtle, such as ‘micro expressions’ (Ekman, *op. cit.*).

Variations in emotional expressions and responses according to particular people or group may suggest that communicating emotion in design is cultural specific. But are design students more emotional? And are design teachers emotional in the studio? Or are these false questions that dichotomise science and art, reason and emotion, where thinking is associated with logic and calculation and emotions with art and beauty? Addressing the perceived dichotomy, Ratner asserts that to separate cognition from emotion or to regard thinking and emotion as different processes, is a misconception (Ratner, 2000). Similarly, Taylor holds that emotions are indispensable for rationality (Taylor, 2001), whereas Stanislavski suggested that, in art, sensuous attention does not mean renouncing reasoning but ‘to reason warmly’ (Stanislavski, 1936).

But while there are many explanations about the relationship between cognition and emotion, everyday studio experiences tell us that emotions can be messy, unpredictable or inconvenient as well as having both creative and destructive potentialities (TenHouten, 2006). For example, freehand sketching in the digital age was found to touch a raw nerve among designers (Jonson, 2005). Yet the role of emotion seems discursively submerged in design education, and its impact on teaching and learning under-researched.

In this paper, I will seek to illuminate the role of emotion in design education drawing from my teaching and learning experience in London design schools, from graphic to product to architectural design, as well as pedagogic research. In this, the studio experience, without assuming universal validity, becomes the research tool as well as research material. But although the enquiry is necessarily partial, the issues involved are topical including the globalisation of design education, the overlapping of art and design disciplines - the ‘design-art’ phenomenon (Coles, 2007), and the relocation of design to the university environment (Buchanan, 2004).

The Studio Experience

Although each design institution, and design domain, has developed its own traditions and practices, it is widely held that central to design is the studio, which can be seen as the embodiment of the ethos of design education (Fisher, 2004). From this perspective, the cultural character of the studio, or “studio culture”, is represented by “the studio model”, an educational model which manifests itself in “the studio experience” where students, and their teachers, engage in constructive problem-solving activities that stimulate sensory exploration and experimentation (“how things might be”). The studio experience, then, reflects both experiential learning (‘thinking *and* doing’; Kolb, 1984) and situated learning (‘context and culture’; Lave & Wenger, 1990) enabling students to become practitioners whilst recognising the need for artistry in professional education (Schön, 1987).

The studio model thus represents an approach to teaching and learning that is both personal and social where learning outcomes are results of individual creations as well as social interactions. The model, moreover, offers substantial pedagogic freedom, including improvisation and play, which stimulates imagination and formation of emotions, as experienced by students in set studio projects. Such rich and authentic learning experiences where students immediately and intuitively find real emotions arising reflect how followers in the creative arts have ‘an intensely personal relationship with their subject’ (Micklethwaite, 2005:92). Personalised learning and social interaction, furthermore, can help students develop meta-cognitive awareness (Flavell, 1979), or ‘meta-emotion’ (Gottman et. al., 1997) that enable them to step back and take the necessary critical view of their own work as a means to change. Through processes of reflection, then, students gain self-knowledge and become more conscious of their ways of thinking and how they channel and manage their emotional energies.

The studio experience, however, also brings individual responsibility because students have to deal with uncertainty, ill-structured problems and conflicting requirements inherent in the processes of design (Cross, 1990). Moreover, teacher-student interaction, like all interpersonal relationships, is potentially manipulative or exploitative resulting in confrontational episodes, for example, fear of embarrassment or failure. The tendency to work with constraints and in adversarial situations is also apparent when the freedom for students to work on their own is removed by pressure to collaborate. Arguably, then, the challenges for students to take responsibility for their actions and emotions include necessarily uncomfortable or unsettling

questions in teacher-student interaction. But to encourage students to take ownership of their emotions also suggests that teachers need to be aware of learners' fears (Sappington 1984) and how to cope with stressful situations ("stress management").

Communicating emotion is thus critical to teacher-student interaction and learning outcomes. But emotional communication is essential to design production too, as observed in the importance given to styling or consumer branding, also described as 'designing emotion' (Desmet, 2002). Norman calls this 'reflective design' and 'is where companies live or die' (Norman, 2004), which underlines the competitive nature of emotional design apparent in the market place when consumers choosing between different products of similar functionality choose the ones with emotional appeal. Ultimately, then, emotion becomes embedded in the work of design. In designing emotion, furthermore, designers could be described as key 'cultural intermediaries', a term that refers to the group of workers who actively promotes consumption through attaching to products and services particular meanings and lifestyles with which consumers will identify (Bourdieu, 1984). To create meaning through design, then, suggests that designers, both in education and professional practice, need to understand *and* empathise with the culture they serve. Design is thus affective both in process and outcome, from idea to market.

Emotion and Learning Theories

There are many different theories of how people learn, and some have been questioned for lack of robustness or rigour, notably learning style models and instruments to personalise the learning experience (Coffield et. al., 2004). However, the criticism of learning styles, which is of interest to this paper, addresses post-16 learning in generic rather than specific settings, that is, classroom rather than studio. Also, the critique seems to underestimate the impact of emotions on teaching and learning – "emotion", for instance, does not appear a key term in the literature search. But although the critics raise legitimate concerns about learning style research, they also concede that an overarching and agreed theory of pedagogy is still far away quoting Alexander's view that 'different ways of knowing and understanding demand different ways of learning and teaching' (Alexander, 2000:561). This suggests that learning theories, at least when discussing experiential learning, are orientational and context dependent rather than prescriptive propositions. For example, in this paper, learning theory may help us understand the role of emotion in the context of design education and the studio experience.

The Studio Experience and Individualism

The intensely personal relationship students have with their subject (Micklethwaite, op. cit.) links the studio experience with humanistic psychology, for instance, self-actualisation, the notion of personal growth towards achieving one's full potential (Maslow, 1968). English design education, however, in asserting individuality and self-reliance, might be seen as propagating hyper-individualism, as in "doing your own thing". For example, research into the experience of international design students in London found that students, in their transition to English design education, were surprised by the demands and freedoms of independent study, which exposed students to stressful situations (Sovič, 2008).

Individuation, then, seems culture-bound and may challenge students from backgrounds where the emphasis is on attending to others, fitting in and harmonious interdependence with them. That is, instead of self-promotion, people are encouraged to restrain their emotions and avoid interpersonal conflicts (Markus and Kitayama, 1991). Yet globalisation of design education in the English mode suggests that design students, irrespective of backgrounds, find themselves absorbing individualism. Thus individualism, as a cultural norm, can be seen as adaptations to problems that people face at different times and in different places (Kagan, 2006). However, hyper-individualism, as displayed in English design culture, and exemplified by the phenomenon of iconic designers ("starchitects" etc), is not without risk: '[design] students are liable to acquire grandiose illusions about the nature of their skills, with the result that they become frustrated in their subsequent careers' (Forty, 1995:241).

Individualism, then, not only highlights the personal aspects of the studio experience but is also congruous with personalised learning, or constructivism, a learning theory pioneered by Piaget whereby learning is understood as a very personal endeavour actively constructed by the learner (Piaget, 1969). Further, personal endeavour holds learners primarily responsible for their emotions. Moreover, the social dimension of the studio experience invites Vygotsky's activity theory where learning is perceived as something that is shaped by social interaction, language, and cultural concepts, and where emotions are interdependent and interpenetrating with other cultural phenomena (Vygotsky, 1962). So while in their respective approach to developmental psychology Piaget places the individual as primary, and Vygotsky social life, both see emotion as a powerful source of knowledge. Both constructivism and activity theory, then, may help explain

why the studio model embodies rich personal, social and emotional experiences that seem to hold firm in a variety of cross-cultural settings.

Reading Rogers into the Studio Experience

The focus on the personal, furthermore, evokes Rogers' theorising from experience on understanding personality and the interpersonal relationship in the facilitation of learning, where he emphasised the attitude of the facilitator, or therapist (Rogers, 1951). Rogers felt that a therapist, in order to be effective, must meet three requirements:

1. Congruence (Realness): genuineness, honesty with the client.
2. Empathy: the ability to feel what the client feels.
3. Respect: acceptance, unconditional positive regard towards the client (Rogers, op. cit.).

Applying these special qualities of the therapist to teachers, and substituting "student" for "client" - Rogers explored the notion of student-centred learning, suggests that the role of the studio teacher is that of facilitator rather than instructor. The teacher as facilitator, moreover, aligns with emotional communication and the view that teachers in creative practices develop a conceptual change/student-focused approach, rather than an information transmission/teacher-focused approach (Trigwell and Prosser, 1996). The student-focused approach, furthermore, situates the studio experience in a social and practice-based learning environment resembling a 'community of practice', described as a social entity where the members act, improvise and share concerns with identity and a common vocabulary (Wenger, 1998). The studio as a community of practice is also reflected in Dewey's insights into the nature and role of habituated behaviors in cementing social ties and reinforcing a sense of community (Dewey, 1916).

Admittedly, transferring Rogers' requirements of the therapist to teachers would be quite demanding and may suggest, controversially, that teaching skills do not matter nearly as much as the teacher's personality. It may be argued, however, that there is no need to set teacher personality against teaching skills. This is so because the studio experience, within a community of practice, provides teachers, and their students, with opportunities to develop their interpersonal (social) and intrapersonal (self-reflection) skills, skills that are embedded in the notion of emotional intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence, EI, described as the ability to perceive, understand, manage and use emotions to facilitate thinking (Salovey and Mayer, op. cit.), builds on the notion of ‘multiple intelligence’ (Gardner, 1983), and other behavioural and psychological theories. Goleman, for example, elaborates on two of Gardner’s seven intelligence types; the interpersonal, i.e. cooperation and teamwork, and the intrapersonal, i.e. self-reflection and self-discovery, also relating the two types to preferred working and learning styles (Goleman, 1995). The interpersonal aspect, then, has to do with understanding others, and their feelings, whereas the intrapersonal aspect relates to understanding yourself, your goals, intentions, responses, and behaviour.

But the notion of emotional intelligence is controversial. For example, ‘... existing research does not yet show that EI exists as a well-defined psychometric and theoretical construct, let alone that it is critical for adaptation for real-world challenges’ (Matthews et. al., 2002:547). Despite their criticism, however, Matthews et. al. recognise the potential of the emotional intelligence construct to educate, to stimulate thought and action, and to spur further study: ‘The benefits of EI appear to reside mainly in raising awareness of emotional issues and motivating educators and managers to take emotional issues seriously’ (Matthews, op. cit. p. 543).

So for example, Mortiboys argues for deliberate, and not just intuitive use of EI in teaching, saying that teachers should recognise and respond to their feelings as well as the feelings of their learners, and encourage a positive emotional state in teacher-student interaction (Mortiboys 2005). But what happens to emotional communication embedded in the studio experience when design education is relocating to the university environment? Do conventional academic fields provide and support a positive emotional learning environment? In other words, how does the culture of design and emotion fit with the academics? This suggests a comparison between the studio model and the university lecture model.

The studio model versus the lecture model

Comparing the two models, it is notable that the lecture model represents a different philosophical tradition, where faculty, through reading and writing academic texts, pays particular

attention to intellectual discourse, rather than the social and emotional aspects of learning. In contrast, the studio model is about experiential learning where teacher-student interaction is mediated by the “object”, rather than “text”, in the tradition of “stuff” and “things”. Thus whereas the lecture model operates largely in the theoretical mode, the studio model mixes the abstract with the visual and the physical.

But words (spoken and written) are the most common means of human communication, both in face-to-face and computer-mediated environments, as experienced by designers (Lawson and Loke, 1997). For example, words, alongside visuals, figure strongly in design presentations, adding emotional vocabulary, or “emotional literacy”, to the languages of graphics and form. Also, histories and theories of design are predominantly word-based and, in the university environment, where writing is the default setting, designers are encouraged to engage in scholarship and the building of design as an academic discipline.

Reflecting on human interaction through language, Hospers asserts: ‘We don’t so much give information, or receive it from what others say, as express our feelings and attitudes and try, through our language, to work on people’s feelings and attitudes in order to change or control them’ (Hospers, 1990:33). Hospers, then, draws our attention to emotional communication, and how information and emotion seem inextricably folded into language, similar perhaps to how it can be difficult to disengage the “information” from the “art” in, say, architects’ drawings.

Yet generic university courses, delivered through the lecture model, have been criticized for not making more of the links between intellectual, social and emotional processes. For example, that learning is facilitated or hampered by emotions (Goleman, *op. cit.*), or that emotions drive learning and memory (Sylvester, 1994). Universities, then, have been slow to make use of social and emotional influences on learning (Love and Goodsell Love, 1995), or, when addressing emotion in educational theory, have failed to show how far the theory is actually practised (Tenenbaum et al, 2001). On this evidence, emotional concerns appear not fully addressed or integrated in the lecture model. This is in contrast to the studio model, as illustrated by the Visual-Auditory-Kinesthetic (VAK) model.

Learning Preferences and the VAK Model

The VAK model emphasises individual learning preferences, and relates to Kolb's learning style model (Kolb, op. cit). According to the model, there are three learning styles:

1. Visual (seeing and reading).
2. Auditory (listening and speaking).
3. Kinesthetic (touching and doing).

The visual learning style involves the use of seen and observed things (for example, images, video, and demonstrations); the auditory style involves listening (words, music, and sounds); and the kinesthetic style involves physical experience (making, touching, and moving).

But whereas the studio and lecture models both include visual and auditory learning styles, the studio model adds the third – kinesthetic. It is kinesthetic learning, then, and notably its “hands-on” and “touchy-feely” qualities, that sets the studio experience apart from learning in the classroom or the lecture hall. Also, and importantly, kinesthetic learning is a working style for designers, exemplified by creative acts such as drawing and other modelling media, giving designers time to reflect on what they are doing while they are doing it, frequently referred to as 'reflection-in-action' (Schön 1983). Such knowing in action enables designers to understand things that cannot be understood just with the eyes, what, in the philosophy of science, has been termed 'tacit knowledge' ('we can know more than we can tell'; Polanyi 1967:4).

The VAK model, then, provides support that the studio model is the learning preference for designers, reflecting Jung's assertion that learning styles result from people's preferred ways of adapting in the world (Jung, 1933). This in turn may help explain why design education, as embodied in the studio experience, is appealing to young people looking for more rewarding, creative challenges and opportunities where they can fully express their emotional needs and desires. Indeed, “Dare to desire!”

Discussion

Although the studio is widely seen as the preferred way of learning and teaching design, the growth in popularity of design education has put the model under pressure. Thus rising student

numbers have not been matched with resources, notably the amount of studio space per student and teacher-student contact hours. But also, digital economics and mobile technologies are changing if not destabilising traditional ways of working while introducing new creative practices and channels of communication. Perhaps the time for the traditional studio model has passed and is now an obstacle to new approaches to teaching and learning design (“what is the studio *for*?”). It then seems necessary to re-examine the studio model as related to emotional communication. For example, in the digital age, does the studio, as learning space, provide critical “emotional space” not experienced elsewhere keeping in mind that learning space informs learning styles, which, in turn, shapes the learning experience?

The relocation of design to the university environment reflects how education, as part of overall culture, takes place within social fields. And social fields, according to Bourdieu, are arenas for the struggle of the resources where individuals, institutions, and other agents try to distinguish themselves from others, and acquire capital, which is useful or valuable on the arena. In modern societies, Bourdieu distinguishes two distinct systems of social hierarchisation. The first is economic, in which position and power are determined by money and property, the capital one commands. The second system is cultural or symbolic, in which one's status is determined by how much cultural or ‘symbolic capital’ one possesses (Bourdieu, op. cit.).

From the perspective of a social field competing for resources, design education can be seen as culture rich but money poor – the studio model demands more resources per student than the lecture model. But although the studio experience is transformational rather than transactional in character, the cultural capital embedded in the studio experience has an exchange value. It may then be argued that in relocating to the university environment, design education profits in economic and symbolic capital (“academic status”) whilst the university gains in cultural capital (“creative status”).

However, in addition to economic and cultural capital, there may be a third system of hierarchisation at play, that is, management. So whereas the studio model represents a fairly flat and self-regulatory organizational structure, the lecture model sits within the regulatory and vertical structure of the university which, like most large organizations, tend to shy away from emotional issues. Having argued that emotional communication is critical to studio culture, this suggests that university-based design would need to raise awareness of emotional issues in higher education discussions, and with both educators and managers. Differences between the studio

model and lecture model in the university environment are perhaps then as much about management as learning styles.

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